

Appendix A

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Your VocabTest.com Test Results

Name:

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You answered **100%** of the questions correctly!
You answered **10 / 10** correctly on the first try.

Vocabulary 3 - Spelling Fill-In - Completed: March 12, 3:13:24 PM CST Unique ID: 123421

Word	Correct*	Incorrect*	Your Answer
advice	100%	0%	Right!
company	92%	8%	Right!
contacts	100%	0%	Right!
enjoy	100%	0%	Right!
fail	92%	8%	Right!
hire	75%	25%	Right!
manager	83%	17%	Right!
own	67%	33%	Right!
risk	100%	0%	Right!
skills	67%	33%	Right!

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Fig. 1 L1G1 Sample Vocabtest Activity

You answered **8 / 10** correctly on the first try.

L3 UNIT 5A LST - Definitions - Completed: May 7, 1:32:02 AM CST Unique ID: 306054806

Word	Definition	Correct*	Incorrect*	Your Answer
complex	not so simple	82%	18%	Right!
connection	joint	82%	18%	Right!
control	supervise	71%	29%	Right!
function	work	88%	12%	Right!
generate	make	76%	24%	Wrong
mood	tendency	71%	29%	Wrong
signals	signs	71%	29%	Right!
speeds	pace	82%	18%	Right!
structure	design	71%	29%	Right!
tiny	very small	82%	18%	Right!

* the percentage of students who answered this correctly or incorrectly

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Fig. 2 L3G12 Sample Vocabtest Activity

Appendix-B

Table 1 L1G1 Paired Samples T-test

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	Test	Statistic	z	df	p	Effect Size	SE Effect Size
FE	-	MTE	Student	6.491		18	< .001	1.489
			Wilcoxon	153.000	3.621		< .001	1.000

Note. For the Student t-test, effect size is given by Cohen's *d* . For the Wilcoxon test, effect size is given by the matched rank biserial correlation.

Table 2 L1G1 Shapiro-Wilk Test

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

	W	p
FE - MTE	0.944	0.312

Note. Significant results suggest a deviation from normality.

Table 3 L1G10 Paired Samples T-test

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	Test	Statistic	z	df	p	Effect Size	SE Effect Size
FE	-	MTE	Student	4.329		15	< .001	1.082
			Wilcoxon	99.500	2.950		0.003	0.895

Note. For the Student t-test, effect size is given by Cohen's *d* . For the Wilcoxon test, effect size is given by the matched rank biserial correlation.

Table 4 L1G10 Shapiro-Wilk Test

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

	W	p
FE - MTE	0.952	0.514

Note. Significant results suggest a deviation from normality.

Table 5 L3G12 Paired Samples T-test

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	Test	Statistic	z	df	p	Effect Size	SE Effect Size	
FE	-	MTE	Student	2.554		22	0.018	0.533	0.156
			Wilcoxon	152.000	2.294		0.022	0.600	0.256

Note. For the Student t-test, effect size is given by Cohen's d . For the Wilcoxon test, effect size is given by the matched rank biserial correlation.

Table 6 L3G12 Shapiro-Wilk Test

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

			W	p
FE	-	MTE	0.951	0.310

Note. Significant results suggest a deviation from normality.

Table 7 L3G14 Paired Samples T-test

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	Test	Statistic	z	df	p	Effect Size	SE Effect Size	
FE	-	MTE	Student	5.710		24	< .001	1.142	0.254
			Wilcoxon	221.500	3.684		< .001	0.918	0.244

Note. For the Student t-test, effect size is given by Cohen's d . For the Wilcoxon test, effect size is given by the matched rank biserial correlation.

Table 8 L3G14 Shapiro-Wilk Test

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk)

			W	p
FE	-	MTE	0.959	0.391

Note. Significant results suggest a deviation from normality.